

IMPROVING THE PROCESS OF EDUCATIONAL AND CREATIVE WORK IN AMATEUR MUSIC PERFORMANCE

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Annotation: Planning and organizing educational and creative activities in an amateur music performance group require the leader to demonstrate sufficient knowledge, skills, and organizational abilities. This article discusses the educational and creative activities within an amateur music performance group and the specific features of their organization.

Keywords: *music performance, creative activities, ensemble, training process, performance skills.*

HAVASKORLIK MUSIQA IJROCHILIGIDA O'QUV-IJODIY ISHLAR JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Havaskorlik musiqa ijrochiligi jamoasidagi o'quv-ijodiy ishlarni rejalashtirish va tashkil etish rahbardan yetarli darajada bilim, ko'nikma va shu bilan birga tashkilotchilik jihatlarini namoyon qilishni talab etadi. Ushbu maqolada havaskorlik musiqa ijrochiligi jamoasidagi o'quv-ijodiy ishlar, ularni tashkil qilishdagi o'ziga xosliklar haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *musiqa ijrochiligi, ijodiy ishlar, ansambl, mashg'ulot jarayoni, ijro qobiliyati.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО И ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ПРОЦЕССА В ЛЮБИТЕЛЬСКОМ МУЗЫКАЛЬНОМ ИСПОЛНЕНИИ

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Аннотация: Планирование и организация учебно-творческой работы в коллективе самодеятельного музыкального исполнения требуют от руководителя достаточных знаний, навыков, а также организационных способностей. В данной статье рассматриваются учебно-творческая деятельность в коллективе самодеятельного музыкального исполнения и особенности их организации.

Ключевые слова: *музыкальное исполнение, творческая деятельность, ансамбль, учебный процесс, исполнительские способности.*

Nowadays, music, physical education, and military-patriotic subjects play an invaluable role in the development of an individual. Enhancing the teaching of these subjects remains a pressing issue

in improving the quality of education in schools [1]. Practical experience of artistic groups shows that a singer's participation in musical performances, regular attendance at rehearsals, and performances at concerts do not automatically lead to the formation of moral and aesthetic culture. In this process, members of a musical performance group must systematically develop their skills and abilities and expand their knowledge of the arts through educational and training activities.

Participants in the group learn to sing, play musical instruments, and dance. However, if educational and training activities are not properly organized, this may affect their ethical behavior. Such a situation indicates a lack of sufficient attention to the overall development, upbringing, moral culture, and behavior of the participants [2].

Amateur musical performance begins with learning to play a specific instrument or sing songs. This process requires great patience and endurance from the student. The challenge becomes even greater due to the limited time available for learning. Unlike music schools or specialized music clubs, where training lasts 5–8 years, amateur musical performance training typically takes between five to six months or up to a year, depending on the performer's abilities and the speed at which they master the material.

To effectively organize the amateur music performance learning process, the teacher must be familiar with methodologies that ensure maximum efficiency with minimal time and effort. When introducing amateur musical performance training, three main formats are used: individual, small group, and collective. Given the need to train 15–20 musicians simultaneously, small group lessons are the most suitable and practical approach. Unlike professional music institutions, where one-on-one instruction is common, the time constraints in amateur music performance make it difficult for an instructor to work individually with each student. Instead, the instructor must conduct group sessions, sometimes organizing 2–3 groups in adjacent rooms, where each group receives a specific assignment and completes it under supervision.

When forming instrumental groups, it is important to consider the abilities and individual differences of the orchestra members. Not all students progress at the same pace. Therefore, during training, special attention should be given to identifying weaknesses in performance and selecting appropriate instructional materials and tools accordingly [3]. During the first year, it is advisable to introduce a variety of tasks to maintain engagement. This period is psychologically challenging for musicians, as their attitude and readiness for rehearsals develop. Repeating the same technical exercises, sound techniques, and strokes for one and a half to two hours can be monotonous. To maintain interest, in addition to mastering proper hand and finger placement, posture, and playing techniques, students should also develop musical literacy, memorize short melodies, and acquire theoretical knowledge. This approach ensures sustained interest in instrumental performance and rehearsals.

Special attention should be given to students who lag behind in performance skills. In group lessons, correcting individual mistakes can be difficult. Organizing individual sessions for struggling musicians allows them to catch up and match the overall level of the orchestra. Additionally, skilled musicians who have mastered their tasks well can be assigned to practice advanced exercises and études [4].

Individual lessons with high-achieving performers accelerate their development as musicians. In the initial stages of instrumental training, lessons should not exceed 40–50 minutes. As students progress, session durations can be extended, focusing on musical literacy and learning the conductor's hand movements.

Once the mastery of instrumental performance and the necessary theoretical knowledge have been acquired, it becomes possible to conduct rehearsals with an orchestra. To reinforce previously covered topics, strengthen theoretical knowledge gained during rehearsals, improve performance techniques, and better memorize musical parts, the conductor may assign homework. However, these tasks should not resemble traditional school assignments. In other words, they should not involve mandatory assessments or grading.

Many participants do not initially realize the complexity of instrumental performance. They tend to perceive mastering an instrument as relatively easy. However, as they begin to grasp the

fundamentals, they may develop a negative attitude toward practicing with the orchestra. In such cases, participants might lose confidence in their abilities and feel as if they are incapable of mastering instrumental performance. Therefore, the leader of an amateur instrumental ensemble should highly acknowledge even small achievements, support the musicians in every possible way, and thus help boost their self-confidence. However, one fundamental rule must be strictly followed: if a participant has not adequately mastered the essential aspects of instrumental performance, it means they have not paid sufficient attention to crucial elements during independent practice.

One of the most important conditions for ensemble performance in an orchestra is the ability of musicians to read notes correctly for the entire group. During the first rehearsal of a selected piece, it is essential to play at a tempo that allows all members of the ensemble to read the notes equally well. In this process, the following aspects should be considered [5]:

- Identifying the position of the note on the instrument;
- Understanding the duration, articulation, and selecting the appropriate stroke for the note;
- Observing the conductor's movements and following their instructions.

To instantly comprehend and respond to such information during performance, musicians must possess solid knowledge and skills. Developing these skills is a long-term process that requires regular, consistent, and well-organized practice sessions. It is advisable to start learning to read notes with simple repertoires, such as well-known folk melodies, simplified versions of piano scores, and compositions written in uncomplicated musical keys with minimal notation. These pieces should generally be composed in a slow tempo to facilitate learning.

To accelerate the process of reading sheet music, it is beneficial to encourage ensemble members to visually analyze their parts, determine the time signature and rhythm of the piece, identify the most challenging sections, arrange finger placement (fingering), and spend a few minutes reading the notes aloud. To further develop the ensemble's note-reading skills, the complexity of pieces should be gradually increased in terms of character, tempo, and dynamics. Each rehearsal should include 15-20 minutes dedicated to note reading.

The success of the ensemble's artistic activities largely depends on how quickly these skills are acquired. The entire process, from learning a piece to performing it, is directly linked to the ability to read and analyze sheet music correctly. This aspect, in turn, plays a crucial role in the ensemble's success, the expansion and renewal of its repertoire, its participation in various cultural events, and, ultimately, gaining recognition from audiences [6].

Conclusion

During this research, I studied the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan related to the field, relevant literature, and the research of experts in this area, leading me to the following conclusion. It is of great importance to focus on extracurricular activities when teaching students both classical and contemporary examples of national culture. The significant achievements in the fields of musical arts, visual arts, and applied arts in our country are not coincidental. These art forms have also gained recognition in foreign countries. Promoting and popularizing the most beautiful examples of national and world culture should be regarded as a crucial aspect of the moral upbringing of the younger generation.

This article serves as a guide for organizing music club activities in general secondary schools, structuring extracurricular educational processes, working with the most widely used choir formats (group singing), and establishing drama clubs, folk instrumental ensembles, dance clubs, vocal and folklore groups, and regulating their activities.

References

1. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-112 dated February 2, 2022, "Madaniyat va san'at sohasini yanada rivojlantirishga doir qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida".
2. Akbarov A. "Musiqqa lug'ati" – Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" Publisher, 1997.
3. Kargin A. "Работы с самодеятельным оркестром русских народных инструментов". –

Moskva: “Musiqa” Publisher, 1984.

4. Toshmatov E. “Dirijorlik” Textbook. – Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati” Publisher, 2008.

5. Toshmatov O‘, Beknazarov X. “Cholg‘ushunoslik” Textbook. – Toshkent: “Turon-Iqbol” Publisher, 2018.

6. Toshmatov O‘, Turatov S. “Ko‘hna cholg‘ular ijrochiligi” Study guide. – Toshkent: “Tafakkur” Publisher, 2016.

7. Muhammadiyev M. HAVASKORLIK MUSIQA IJROCHILIGI JAMOASIDAGI O‘QUV-IJODIY ISHLAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH //Nordic_Press. – 2024. – T. 5. – №.0005.